

2-Phenyl-2-methyl-3-aryl-thiazolidin-4-ones as Potential Antitubercular Compounds

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2-Phenyl-2-methyl-3-aryl-thiazolidin-4-ones have been prepared by addition of thioglycolic acid to substituted azomethines in benzene. The azomethines were prepared by KOH treatment of α -cyano-amines which were in turn obtained by reaction of aromatic amines, acetophenone and KCN. Two representative compounds have indicated good antitubercular activity.

THIAZOLIDINONES exhibit antitubercular¹, hypnotic², anaesthetic³ and antifungal⁴ activities. In continuation of our previous work⁵ on thiazolidinones we report here the synthesis of 2-phenyl 2-methyl-3-aryl-thiazolidin-4-ones (I) as potential antitubercular substances. Azomethines are suitable starting material for preparation of (I). The method using ZnCl₂ gave impure and poor yield of anils. Earlier Desai and others⁶ prepared ($\pm$)- α -amino-nitriles of γ -camphor and Dhanani, Undavia and Thaker⁷ prepared and resolved ($\pm$)- α -amino-nitriles of acetophenones. In our case we used α -aminophenyl acetonitriles and treated it with hot KOH immediately to yield azomethines. These were treated with thioglycolic acid under standard conditions to give thiazolidinones (I). 2-Phenyl-2-methyl-3-phenyl-thiazolidin-4-one and 2-phenyl-2-methyl-3-(4-carboxyphenyl)-thiazolidin-4-one (Table 1) showed good activity against H_s, R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Experimental

Preparation of α -cyano amines: KCN (0.1 M) was dissolved in water (12 ml) and acetophenone (0.1 M) was added. The flask was cooled in ice-bath and glacial acetic acid (0.1 M) added dropwise. After about 15 min, amine (0.1 M) and ethanol (95%) were added to clear the solution and left overnight. The product filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol. Yields 85%, $\nu_{\max}$ 2230 (CN), 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Schiff bases: A solution of methanolic KOH (0.03 M) (100 ml) was added to α -cyanoamine (0.01 M) in hot methanol (50 ml) and refluxed for 45 min, cooled, water (100 ml) added and extracted with benzene. The solvent layer concentrated to give azomethines. ($\nu_{\max}$ 1640-1650 cm⁻¹).

Thiazolidine-4-ones: Azomethine (0.01 M), benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.012 M) were refluxed (app. 25 hr) using Dean-Stark water separator. The solvent removed and the residue treated with NaHCO₃ solution and filtered. The thiazolidinones recrystallised from EtOH, yield 45%. $\nu_{\max}$ 750 (-C-S), 1620, 1650 cm⁻¹ (-Co-N).

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE

(a)

(I)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C (a)	m.p. °C (I)	Antitubercular activity**
1.	phenyl*	156	165	+
2.	4-Cl-phenyl	141	175	
3.	3-Cl-phenyl	135	195	
4.	2-CH ₃ -phenyl	118	168	
5.	3-CH ₃ -phenyl	137	175	
6.	4-CH ₃ -phenyl	144	187	
7.	4-COOH-phenyl*	207	267	+
8.	α -naphthyl	140	182	
9.	4-Br-phenyl	145	175	
10.	4-OMe-phenyl	108	180	

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N, S analysis.

* Compounds tested for anti T. B. activity in preliminary screening.

** Compounds showing activity against *M. tuberculosis* H_s, R_v strain at a concentration of 0.5 mg/ml and 2.0 mg/ml.

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